

Dynamic management of processes and communicators in malleable MPI applications

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Abstract—A malleable application is defined as one that can increase or decrease its resources dynamically based on workload variations. These applications often leverage a job manager to handle the resources. For MPI applications, the standard incorporates some strategies to increase the number of processes connected to a running application. However, it does not clarify how to use these same features to reduce said processes. In this paper, a strategy compatible with the latest version of the MPI standard to develop malleable MPI applications is presented. It allows the addition and removal of resources at the computing node level in a discretionary manner. The results obtained from the evaluation show that the proposed strategy has acceptable performance and scalability for the functionality it provides.

Index Terms—MPI, Malleability, Reconfigurable applications, HPC resource management

I. INTRODUCTION

High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems have grown tremendously in recent years. This forces applications to adapt to new systems where the number of processors is constantly growing, connected by increasingly fast communication networks.

These systems are designed to manage an increasing number of applications at the same time. For that purpose, resource and work management applications are used to select the applications to be executed at any given moment. As HPC system resources increase, it is necessary to run more concurrent applications to maintain efficient use of resources. This, however, complicates the simultaneous scheduling of multiple jobs with very different resource needs, execution times, and workloads.

One possible solution is the introduction of malleable tasks. A malleable task is defined as one that can increase or decrease its resources during its execution, depending on its needs or the global scheduling needs of the system. Malleability can increase the scheduler's chances of improving the system's effectiveness. For example, a running application can increase its resources once other applications finish, thus reducing its overall execution time. Another application could take advantage of unused resources while the scheduler is waiting to get enough for a large application.

One of the most widely used development environments for HPC applications is MPI. This platform eases up the development of distributed parallel applications. For example, MPI communicators allow the application processes to be collectively connected. The MPI environment was initially designed for launching applications with a fixed number of

connected processes. However, over time, diverse functionalities have been introduced into the standard, allowing new processes to be dynamically generated and connected to the MPI application. However, up to now, a definitive solution for the development of malleable applications has not been established in the standard. On the one hand, the MPI standard proposes some options to increase the processes of an application. However, it does not clarify which is the correct way to reduce that number of processes.

There are other alternatives to change the number of processes, like the ones based on checkpointing and relaunching the application. These techniques are easier to implement but lack the flexibility and performance of properly malleable applications [1]. Currently, malleable applications are rare [2].

This paper introduces a new malleable strategy, which is compatible with the latest version of the MPI standard (specifically version 4.0 [3] but dynamic process features were introduced in MPI 2.0 [4]) to improve the development of malleable MPI applications. These features can be used in conjunction with existing job managers for HPC systems.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the II section illustrates various related state-of-the-art proposals; the III section shows the main concepts used in this work; section IV presents the proposed strategy for the development of malleable MPI applications; the V section shows the evaluation of the proposed techniques; and finally, the VI section shows the conclusions and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

In the literature, there are various proposals to develop malleable MPI applications. On the one hand, there are various options based on relaunching the application once a data checkpoint has been completed. For example, there is the proposal called PCM (Process Checkpointing and Migration)[5]. This work conceives malleability as a succession of operations to divide and integrate processes based on adding calls from the PCM environment in the application itself. Other Options that follow a similar scheme are the Checkpointing/scalable restart techniques [6], the proposal called SRS (Stop Restart Software) [7], and the Adaptive MPI (AMPI)[8]. In general, these options usually follow the strategy of saving the data to disk, terminating existing processes, relaunching a new series of processes, and recovering the data from disk. There is another proposal [9] that combines AMPI with the Torque/Maui resource manager and extends it for use with malleable jobs.

Other options are, for example, Elastic MPI [10] which includes an infrastructure and a set of MPI extensions for executing malleable MPI applications. This implementation is based on MPICH and Slurm so its main drawback is being dependent on both.

Another state-of-the-art proposal is FlexMPI [11], [12] which also implements extensions to have malleable applications. FlexMPI also provides application monitoring and different automatic strategies to select which processes to modify and when, and provides data redistribution with load balancing.

Similar to the last one, in [13], the authors present DMRLib, a library that provides process malleability features using a minimalist MPI-like syntax. It also includes different scalability patterns and two different job submission modes (rigid and moldable) but lacks the data redistribution part.

ULFM (User Level Failure Migration) [14] is another of the existing options. ULFM is a non-standard extension of MPI to incorporate malleability by integrating the fault tolerance mechanisms included in ULFM with the existing dynamic reconfiguration mechanisms in MPI (*MPI_Comm_spawn*).

In the work carried out in [15], all the functionalities present in the MPI standard that may be relevant for the development of parallel applications are analyzed in detail, as well as different strategies to implement said applications.

The proposed solution is a merging technique (following the classification in [14]) instead of a baseline (or checkpointing/restart) technique. To expand the application, new MPI processes are added to the old ones, and to shrink the application, some MPI processes are terminated, while the rest continue executing. Also, our proposal effectively terminates all the processes running on any node that has been added before with this technique. It happens while the processes of the other nodes continue the execution of the application. This technique, in combination with the Slurm, features to increase or reduce dynamically the number of nodes assigned to a job, allowing a shrinking application to free some nodes that will be used by other applications without stopping the current one.

This feature of terminating the removed processes when shrinking the application is in contrast with the shrinking methodology for the merge technique proposed in [14] and in other frameworks like FlexMPI [11], [12] that relies on setting the removed processes as zombies until the end of the application. This approach does not allow reusing the resources of the removed processes until the application ends, which our technique does. However, to terminate all processes on a node, they should constitute a single MPI process group executed using a single *srun* call. This is automatic when using *MPI_Comm_spawn* on MPICH integrated with Slurm. However, due to restrictions in other frameworks (like OpenMPI), we are currently developing other ways to achieve the same result for them.

III. BACKGROUND

A. Dynamic process management in MPI

Initially, the MPI standard did not allow the creation of new processes during the application execution. New functionalities have been included in version 2 to dynamically extend the processes of an MPI application. In its purest concept, an MPI application is based on the SPMD (Single Program Multiple Data) models. However, due to the inclusion of these new functionalities, applications can follow both an SPMD model, with a dynamic number of processes, and change to an MPMD model (Multiple Programs Multiple Data) where the new processes can execute a different program from the original one.

The MPI standard (up to version 4.0) implements two different strategies to dynamically manage the number of processes. These strategies can be listed as:

- 1) Creation of new processes generated from the MPI application code itself and later integrated as part of said application.
- 2) Launch of two MPI applications independently that are later integrated into a single application.

In the first case, the semantics are similar to creating a UNIX process. It is done using the *MPI_Comm_spawn* or *MPI_Comm_spawn_multiple* function calls. These calls allow launching a new group of processes executing the same, or different, programs indicated as parameters (note the difference between SIMD and MIMD). This group of new processes behaves in many ways like a new MPI application, with its own communicator *MPI_COMM_WORLD*. The *MPI_Comm_spawn* call at the parent process and the *MPI_Comm_get_parent* call at the child process return an inter-communicator communicating both *MPI_COMM_WORLD*.

In the second case, the semantics are similar to those used for sockets. It requires two MPI applications running, one is the server and the other is the client. In the server application, a communications port is open with the call *MPI_Open_port*. Then the *MPI_Comm_accept* call is executed to wait for a connection request. The client application processes execute the *MPI_Comm_connect* call, creating the connection to the server application. In this case, both applications also receive a special communicator (inter-communicator) as a result.

In both cases, the new group of processes has its own *MPI_COMM_WORLD* communicator. However, it can communicate with the rest of the processes using the *inter-communicator* generated along the way. An inter-communicator allows the connection (via a point-to-point connection) of two intra-communicators (like the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* of two different groups of processes). An inter-communicator can be transformed into a normal intra-communicator. However, the standard does not guarantee that its performance is the same as that of a pure intra-communicator.

Below we will list the most relevant characteristics of both strategies related to the objective of creating and managing malleable applications with MPI:

- The *MPI_Comm_spawn* call in parent processes and the *MPI_Init* call in child processes are (potentially) collective with each other. Also, the *MPI_Comm_get_parent* call can only be made in the *MPI_Init/ MPI_Finalize* context. This means that communicators created from *MPI_Comm_spawn* cannot be used with other alternatives such as MPI sessions.
- *MPI_Finalize* is a collective call between all processes that are connected by a communicator at the time of calling that function. Also, a process cannot disconnect from the communicator *MPI_COMM_WORLD* before making the call to *MPI_Finalize*. This implies that all processes belonging to the same group (whether created at startup or via *MPI_Comm_spawn*) have to terminate at the same time.
- The *MPI_Comm_accept* and *MPI_Comm_connect* calls can be made as many times as you like between any two groups of processes connected to each other by a communicator. It doesn't matter if they are from the same MPI application or not.

B. Integration with Job Scheduler (Slurm)

The MPI standard was designed to facilitate communications, among other interactions, between application processes. However, it does not contemplate the management of those processes and the resources necessary for their creation/destruction. The task of managing these resources is usually carried out by a job scheduler, and one of the best-known and most frequently used is the Slurm job manager.

Slurm (Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management) is a resource management system for an HPC system. It provides a flexible platform for managing tasks, assigning resources, and scheduling jobs in a distributed environment. In addition, it facilitates efficient resource management, job monitoring, and the implementation of custom allocation policies. Slurm uses work queues to manage and prioritize tasks submitted by users. Tasks are executed based on assignment policies. These can take into account factors such as user priority, resource availability, and time constraints.

Slurm is based on two basic operations that complement each other. These operations are:

- Reservation of the resources requested by the application: Especially the reservation of computing nodes, but it can also be individual CPUs, memory, etc. A given pool of resources is called a *job* or work. This operation can be performed with the Slurm *salloc* command.
- Creation and management of application processes: It requires that there be a prior reservation of resources. The processes created will use all or part of said resources. A given execution of the processes of an application is called a *job step* or job stage. A job can run multiple stages in parallel (distributing resources) or sequentially. This operation can be performed with the Slurm *srun* command.

Below we list the most relevant characteristics of Slurm operations when creating and managing malleable applications with MPI:

- Slurm allows a running job to dynamically increase its resources (especially the number of nodes). The new resources are booked with a new job. When the job is running, it is integrated into of the old one and the resources are aggregated.
NOTE: Latest version Of Slurm has eliminate the possibility of increasing the number of nodes of a running job (they can be added if the job is pending). Therefore a new approach should be used then (like using more than one job for a single application).
- Slurm allows a running job to reduce its resources (especially the number of nodes). The only requirement is that these resources are not currently being used by one of the work stages. This operation is performed with the Slurm *scontrol* command.
- Slurm allows a job to execute as many job stages as desired either in parallel (spreading out resources) or sequentially.
- To the best of our knowledge, Slurm does not allow reducing the resources assigned to a work stage until said stage is completely finished.

The relation between MPI and job managers like Slurm is mixed. Each MPI implementation has its own way of working with job managers. There are three main strategies to carry out this integration.

- Null integration: It is the most basic option. The job manager is solely in charge of booking the resources While the MPI environment is exclusively in charge of creating and managing the application processes.
- Tailor-made integration: The MPI framework leverage the features of the job manager to perform the creation and management of processes. This integration is done ad-hoc for each job manager.
- Integration based on a standard: In this case, the operation is similar to the previous case with the exception that a standard is used to perform this integration. The most widely used is the PMI (Process Management Interface) standard, created to provide an interface for managing and coordinating processes in high-performance computing environments. There are three versions (PMI-1, PMI-2[16], and PMIx[17]) being the last one a development designed to address the challenges of large-scale systems (exascale).

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF MALLEABLE MPI APPLICATIONS

A. Project background: Intelligent Controller (IC)

The proposal presented in this paper is part of a bigger ongoing project whose goal is to fulfill the malleability of HPC systems while solving many of the issues regarding this objective. One of the project's main features is the inclusion of a centralized decision system to determine how to better redistribute the resources among all malleable applications

running on the system. This decision system is called the Intelligent Controller (IC)

Many other state-of-the-art solutions leverage their own custom framework to deal with resource managers (RMS) and the different MPI frameworks (and others). The idea is to use this custom framework as an abstraction layer in charge of performing the malleable operations (as in [12] and [13]). The advantage is that applications do not need to manage these things on their own. In this project, the goal is to coordinate several malleable applications at once. This is where the need for a centralized decision system (like the IC) arises.

The IC is a multi-criteria distributed component that integrates cross-layer data to have a holistic view of the system and uses it to dynamically facilitate decisions for resource allocation. Note that in our case, the applications can request resources (more or less), but it is the IC in coordination with Slurm who assigns them or not.

Considering this perspective, the main roles of the IC are (among others): to collect information to define the current system status through a monitoring system, make intelligent analyses of status information, and leverage this analysis to make efficient malleability decisions to increase the throughput, and send back this decisions to the applications.

The applications do not have to handle these decisions on their own. Instead, they can leverage a local framework design to perform the malleability decisions received from the IC. All the strategies presented in this paper will be included in this framework.

B. Description of the proposal

The basic functionality behind a malleable MPI application is the addition or removal of processes during its execution. The goal is to adapt the application to the available resources. The new set of processes is integrated by creating a global communicator that covers all of them (the original ones and the ones created dynamically). This communicator needs to be adjusted dynamically to mimic the changes.

This paper introduces a new proposal for the implementation of this kind of malleable MPI application. The proposal is designed to be executed in an HPC cluster with a booking granularity at the node level. The requirements considered are the following:

- The application must reserve an initial number of nodes to start its execution.
- The application may reserve new nodes to increase its number of processes dynamically.
- The application may free nodes when the processes running on that node end.
- The application may choose the nodes to remove. This is limited to dynamic nodes only.

As mentioned in III-A, the MPI standard (up to version 4.0) has some limitations that make it difficult to achieve these conditions. The main one requires the creation or destruction of all the processes belonging to a group at the same time. In this context, we define the term group of processes as the set of processes that are connected to the

same *MPI_COMM_WORLD* communicator. There are two mechanisms to create a group of processes:

- Launching an MPI application.
- Executing an *MPI_Comm_spawn* collective call.

The technique proposed is based on this concept and it can be summarized as follows:

- Initially, the MPI application is created with the minimum number of nodes that are considered acceptable.
- Each time a *MPI_Comm_spawn* call is executed, a new group of processes group is created. We limit each new group to the processes belonging to a single node.
- When all the processes of the same group end, the associated node is removed.

Every time there is a modification in the number of nodes, the global communicator has to be updated. It is obtained by combining all the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* and/or *MPI_COMM_SELF* communicators cumulatively. The composition has to be done in pairs. For each pair, an inter-communicator should be temporarily generated to obtain the desired intra-communicator.

There are two strategies to combine the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* communicators of two groups of processes. The first one is applied when one of the groups is created using *MPI_Comm_spawn*. In this case, the communicator used in the *MPI_Comm_spawn* is combined with the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* of the new group. This is perfect for adding new nodes (one by one). However the removal has a caveat, it can only remove the last added node. In summary, the adding and removal of nodes behave like a FIFO queue.

The second strategy requires the use of *MPI_Comm_accept* and *MPI_Comm_connect*. This allows it to combine any two communicators of my choosing. The goal is to combine bigger and bigger communicators until they achieve the desired global communicator. This strategy can be executed many times, without limitation, to any subset of processes connected to an existing communicator. That makes it ideal for removing any node we choose, as long as its processes belong to a single *MPI_COMM_WORLD*. However, it could also be used for adding new nodes as long as their groups of processes are launched as independent MPI applications and the mpi port name is shared among them.

Removing a node may require disconnecting the previous global communicator completely. That means disconnecting all the communicators involved in its creation. Therefore, all these partial communicators have to be stored with the global communicator so they all can be disconnected at once.

Algorithm 1 implements the strategy proposed to add new nodes using *MPI_Comm_spawn*. The algorithm uses a loop to call *MPI_Comm_spawn* once for every new node added. The global communicator is done incrementally merging the aggregated communicator with the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* of the new group of processes.

Algorithm 2 implements another version of the previous strategy using *MPI_Comm_accept/MPI_Comm_connect*. This

strategy requires the use of the local framework that connects both the application and the IC. This framework offers a service to launch any MPI application with parameters on another job allocated by Slurm. As mentioned in Section III the latest version of Slurm cannot expand a running job. Therefore, the only way to create a new group of processes is to launch the application again on another job. The address of the port to perform the connection is given as a parameter. The algorithm uses a loop to launch the application in all the nodes and then another loop to connect using *MPI_Comm_accept* once for every new node added. The global communicator is done incrementally merging the aggregated communicator with the *MPI_COMM_WORLD* of the new group of processes.

Algorithm 3 implements the strategy to reduce the nodes in a malleable MPI application. First, a new global communicator is created with the remaining nodes. Later, the old communicator is disconnected along with all its partial communicators. The global communicator is built incrementally following the structure of a binary tree. Initially, all the groups are paired to get a composite communicator for each pair. These communicators are paired again to create new composite communicators. This step is repeated until all processes are contained in a single global communicator. Given its binary tree structure, the complexity of this algorithm is of order $O(\log_n)$ where n is the number of the nodes.

Algorithm 1: Add new nodes in a malleable MPI application using *MPI_Comm_spawn*

Input : Comm_Global, New_Nodes

Output: Comm_Global

```

// If child process, connect it
1 if is_child_process then
2   Inter_Comm = MPI_Get_parent();
3   New_Nodes = MPI_Receive(Inter_Comm);
4   Comm_Global = MPI_Merge(Inter_Comm);

// Repeat if there are nodes to add
5 while Non_empty(New_Nodes) do
6   node = get_first_one(New_Nodes);
7   delete_first_one(New_Nodes);
8   Inter_Comm=MPI_spawn(node,Comm_Global);
9   MPI_Send(New_Nodes, Inter_Comm);
10  Comm_Global = MPI_Merge(Inter_Comm);

```

V. EVALUATION

In this section, we present the evaluation of the proposed solution. We focus the evaluation on the performance and scalability of the proposal. Initially, we evaluate the algorithms proposed for adding and removing nodes. In any case we evaluate both, the creation and destruction of the global communicator. Finally, we apply this methodology to execute a use case, a CFD kernel called WaComM++. The idea is to test if this method has any influence on the performance compared to allocating all nodes at once. In this section, we

Algorithm 2: Add new nodes in a malleable MPI application using *accept/connect*

Prog. Parameters: Port_Name, Pos

Input : Comm_Global, Num_Nodes

Output : Comm_Global

```

1 Comm_Global = MPI_COMM_WORLD;
2 if is_empty(Port_Name) then
3   Port_Name = MPI_Open_port();
4   for i=0; i<Num_Nodes; i++ do
5     | launch_app (app, Port_Name, Pos+i);
6   end
7   for i=0; i<Num_Nodes; i++ do
8     | Inter = MPI_accept (Comm_Global);
9     | Comm_Global = MPI_Merge(Inter);
10  end
11 else
12  Inter=MPI_connect (Port_Name, Comm_Global);
13  Comm_Global = MPI_Merge(Inter);
14  for i=Pos; i<Num_Nodes; i++ do
15    | Inter = MPI_accept (Comm_Global);
16    | Comm_Global = MPI_Merge(Inter);
17  end
18 end

```

present the evaluation of the proposed solution. We focus the evaluation on the performance and scalability of the proposal. Initially, we evaluate the algorithms proposed for adding and removing nodes. In any case we evaluate both, the creation and destruction of the global communicator. Finally, we apply this methodology to execute a use case, a CFD kernel called WaComM++. The idea is to test if this method has any influence on the performance compared to allocating all nodes at once.

The architecture of the system used for the evaluation consists of a cluster of 68 nodes where each one includes 2 Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2697 processors at 3.4 Ghz, each with 18 cores. The nodes have 128 GB of available RAM. Communications are handle by a 100 Gb/s Omni-Path network. The software layer includes Slurm version 22.05 and MPICH version 4.0.3. MPICH is using the UCX driver to access the Omni-Path network. The tests have been scaled up to 20 nodes (720 processes).

Figure 1 shows the performance when adding up to 18 new nodes to an application running on a single node. On the one hand, it shows how long it takes to add all the nodes in a single *MPI_Comm_spawn* call. On the other hand, it shows the time taken to launch the nodes one by one through successive calls to *MPI_Comm_spawn*. Finally, it also shows how long it takes to include a new node when the application already has all nodes but one.

The figure shows that the execution of a single call to *MPI_Comm_spawn* is practically the same (around 1.5 seconds) regarding the number of nodes (newly added or already executing). This means that the chosen strategy of increasing the application node by node may have a significant cost as the number of nodes increases.

Algorithm 3: Remove nodes in a malleable MPI application

```

Input : Comm_Global, deleted_Nodes
Output: Comm_Global

// Select nodes to delete
1 Group = get_Process_Group(Comm_Global);
2 Deleted = is_In(Group, deleted_Nodes);

// Open port in each remaining group
3 Rank = MPI_Rank(MPI_COMM_WORLD);
4 if Rank==0 AND NO(Deleted) then
5 |   Port = MPI_open_port();
6 end

// Sharing port addresses
7 Vec_Ports=MPI_Allgather(Port,Comm_Global);

// Deleted->disconnect comm. and finish
8 if Deleted then
9 |   MPI_Disconnect(Comm_Global);
10 |  MPI_Finalize();
11 |  exit(0);
12 end

// Getting the groups that remain
13 Vec_Group_Val = get_valids(Vec_Ports);
14 Group_Val = position(Group, Vec_Group_Val);
15 Num_Group_Val = size(Vec_Group_Val);

// Joint the MPI_COMM_WORLD -> Comm_Global
16 Comm_Local = MPI_COMM_WORLD;
17 while Num_Group_Val > 1 do
18 |   Index = Group_Val % Num_Group_Val;
19 |   if Index == Group then
20 | |   Inter = MPI_accept (Comm_local);
21 | |   Comm_local = MPI_Merge(Inter);
22 |   else
23 | |   Port=get_Port(Vec_Ports, Index);
24 | |   Inter=MPI_connect (Port, Comm_local);
25 | |   Comm_local = MPI_Merge(Inter);
26 |   end
27 |   Num_Group_Val = Num_Group_Val / 2;
28 end

// Disconnect the comm. global
29 MPI_Disconnect(Comm_Global);

// Get next global comm.
30 Comm_Global = Comm_local;

```

Figure 2 shows the performance when adding up to 18 new nodes using the accept/connect approach. The results do not include the launching of the application as this can be done before hand in the background. The results also show an incremental cost proportional to the number of nodes but with a much smaller scale.

Figure 3 shows the time needed to create a new global communicator with the processes from an existing communicator using *MPI_Comm_accept* / *MPI_Comm_connect*. On the one hand the communicator is built using the

Figure 1: Inclusion of new nodes: Spawn and generation of the associated communicator.

Figure 2: Inclusion of new nodes: Launching a separate application and using accept/connect.

Figure 3: Removing nodes: New global communicator using accept/connect.

MPI_COMM_WORLD communicators. On the other hand we use the *MPI_COMM_SELF* communicators. The test follows the binary tree scheme for the creation of the communicators.

The results show that this strategy is highly scalable. The bi-

Figure 4: Removing nodes: Global communicator deletion.

Figure 5: Wacomm Execution: Growing the number of nodes.

nary tree connection scheme considerably reduces the number of operations as the number of nodes or processes increases, which is expected from an algorithm of $O(\log_n)$ complexity. In addition, the times are below the second, even when 720 processes are linked individually.

Finally, Figure 4 present the time required to disconnect a global communicator including all the partial ones used to generate it. On the one hand, it shows the disconnection of a global communicator generated incrementally (with *MPI_Comm_spawn*). On the other hand, it shows the disconnection of a global communicator generated with the binary tree scheme (*MPI_Comm_accept* / *MPI_Comm_connect*) either from *MPI_COMM_WORLD* and from *MPI_COMM_SELF*.

The result implies negligible disconnection times (below 100 microseconds). In any case, the time seems proportional to the number of partial communicators disconnected. Therefore, global communicators generated incrementally take longer to disconnect than those generated with the binary tree scheme.

Finally, we present the execution of a use case, a CFD kernel called *WaComM++* (Water Community Model). *WaComM++* is a pollutant transport and diffusion model that operates over the model outputs. It is a Lagrangian model that simulates marine pollutants' transport and diffusion processes. *WaComM++* is a component of the *Environment Application* workflow that produces operational weather and marine forecasts and/or on-demand ad-hoc environmental simulations for scenarios and what-if analysis [18]. *WaComM++* is characterized by a parallelization schema based on hierarchical and heterogeneous computation. The *WaComM++* code is based on iterative computation. On each iteration, the total number of particles are distributed by the root process among all the available processors in an MPI distributed memory fashion. Once all particles are processed the results are gather by the root process.

Figure 5 shows the performance of the execution of one *WaComM++* iteration with different number of nodes (form 1 to 20). On the one hand, the application is set to grow one node at a time using the method presented here. On the other hand

Figure 6: Wacomm Execution: Reducing the number of nodes.

the application is launched from the start with this number of nodes. It is important to notice that only the execution of the iteration is presented here. The time required to grow or shrink the application is not included. Nevertheless, this information is already contemplated on earlier experiments.

The results confirm that the proposed method do not present any drawback on the performance of the application if not for the time required to perform the grow/shrink procedures. Both approaches shows almost the same performance as was expected from the beginning.

Figure 6 also shows the performance of the execution of one *WaComM++* iteration with different number of nodes but in this case following a shrinking trend (from 20 to 1). On the one hand, the application is set to grow, one node at a time using the method presented here, until it reaches a total of 20 nodes. Afterwards it proceeds to shrink the nodes, also one at a time until it reaches the desired number. On the other hand the application is launched from the start with this number of nodes. As before, the time required to grow or shrink the application is not included.

The results confirm that both approaches show almost the same performance. Therefore, as expected, we can conclude

that the proposed method do not present any drawback on the performance of the application apart from the time required to perform the grow/shrink procedures.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we present a novel methodology to develop malleable MPI applications. This proposal allows the system to add and remove resources (nodes) dynamically on demand, leveraging both the facilities present in the MPI 4.0 standard, as well as the existing integration with Job Schedulers such as Slurm. The proposed technique handles the granularity at the node level. Two new strategies to increase the nodes of the application have been presented. The first one is based on the `MPI_Comm_spawn` call. The second one is based on the `MPI_Comm_accept / MPI_Comm_connect` calls with an ad-hoc service to launch the application. Another strategy to reduce the nodes of the application has been presented, removing nodes among those dynamically added.

The performed evaluation shows that the adding technique based on `MPI_Comm_spawn` has an important overload due to the serialization of the creation of the groups of processes. This effect could be avoided in the future by performing it in the background. The other technique based on `MPI_Comm_accept / MPI_Comm_connect` split the launching from the creation of the communicator which makes it easier to hide the effects in the background. The removing technique shows a good performance and scalability.

In future works, we intend to research new methods to enhance the performance of the adding strategy. The goal is to increase the performance without losing malleability .

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been developed within the framework of the European Union (European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking) through the project “Adaptive multi-tier intelligent data manager for Exascale” with reference No 956748 - ADMIRE - H2020-JTI - EuroHPC- 2019-1, and the Spanish Research Agency with project reference PCI2021-121966.

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